

Leaders, institutions, or context? Explaining local government compliance with transparency regulations in Romania

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Abstract

The paper proposes a contextualized approach to local government transparency and its determinants. It starts by briefly discussing the distinction between local government compliance with transparency regulations and broader/more substantial local government transparency. A context-dependent measure of local government compliance with transparency regulation is built for the Romanian case and used to showcase significant variation from one local government to the next. Next, the paper approaches a set of inter-related questions concerning the predictors of compliance: Which previously identified predictors of compliance are also relevant in the Romanian context? Does external pressure exercised by the central government and/or civil society increase compliance with transparency provisions? In a strong leader local government system, how strong is the influence of the characteristics of the political leader in explaining compliance? The analysis finds that Romania has a distinct profile in terms of explanatory factors of local government compliance with transparency regulations. Characteristics of the local political and institutional environment such as the status, size, and financial autonomy of local governments are found to be relevant for understanding compliance in Romania. The paper also provides some points for practitioners.

Keywords

transparency; compliance; local government; Romania; transparency policy

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Introduction

Political science has given significant attention to building measurements of local government transparency, applying them to uncover between and within country variation and to identify the explanatory factors of this variation. Results have been mixed and rather difficult to integrate into a broader picture. Difficulties seem to start with defining and measuring local government transparency, with some researchers building comprehensive theory-based definitions of transparency and others focusing on compliance with a set of transparency regulations in each country. Difficulties continue as researchers try to identify a unique set of factors explaining transparency. The efforts to build an explanatory model have led to the same factor being identified as relevant in multiple national contexts, only to find that in some countries it stimulates transparency while in others it acts as an inhibitor. Taking these aspects into account, more recent literature (Michener, 2019; Pozen, 2020) argues that more contextualized research is needed.

This paper proposes such a contextualized approach. It aims to answer the following set of inter-related research questions relevant for both the case studied and broader transparency literature: Which previously identified predictors of compliance are also relevant in the Romanian context? Does external pressure exercised by the central government and/or civil society increase compliance with transparency provisions? In a strong leader local government system, how strong is the influence of the characteristics of the political leader in explaining compliance? The empirical approach focuses on building a context-adequate measurement of compliance with transparency provisions as well as an explanatory framework. This framework focuses on the influence of individual, political, and institutional, and contextual (social and economic) factors over compliance.

The paper is structured as follows. The second section discusses local government transparency compliance, with a focus on its measurement and explanatory factors. The third section introduces the national context of this study. The fourth discusses methodological aspects. The fifth section presents the results of the analysis, while the final one discusses them.

Defining, measuring, and explaining local government transparency: a literature review

Governmental transparency is usually defined as the ability of citizens to see inside the processes and structures of government (Grigorescu, 2002; Piotrowski and Van Ryzin, 2007; Etzioni, 2010). In democratic regimes, transparency is demanded by civil society at all levels of government and often subject to national government policymaking. Thus, national governments create rules applicable to local governments and enforce compliance, although effectiveness seems limited (Berliner, 2016; Michener and Nichter, 2022). This seems a straightforward path towards tangible and measurable local government transparency. Researchers have thus paid significant attention to measuring local government transparency (see Bauhr and Grimes, 2012; da Cruz et al., 2016).

Efforts to better specify the concept have led to the identification of three different subspecies of transparency, applicable to all government levels: financial (budget, use of public resources), administrative (operation of bureaucracy), and political (information on elected bodies and political representatives) (Cucciniello, Porumbescu and Grimmelhuisen, 2017). However, researchers in different national contexts have operationalized local government transparency differently (Piotrowski, 2010; Cucciniello and Nasi, 2014; Araujo and Tejedo-Romero, 2016; da Cruz et al., 2016; Spáč, Voda and Zagravan, 2018; Tavares and da Cruz, 2020). Efforts to tailor measurement to the national context go as far as structuring an index of transparency in a participatory process (da Cruz et al., 2016). This variation in measurement reflects the extent to which researchers have focused on compliance with varied sets of regulations or a more complex (maybe one-size-fitting-all) meaning of transparency.

Table 1. Explanatory factors of higher local government transparency / compliance with transparency regulations.

Explanatory factor	References	Countries and observations
<i>Characteristics of the local political leaders</i>		
Gender - female mayor or the proportion of female councillors	(Araujo and Tejedo-Romero, 2016; Tavares and da Cruz, 2020)	Spain, Portugal
Ideology – left-wing (or progressive) political leader or largest party in the council	(Alt, Lassen and Rose, 2006; Albalate del Sol, 2013; Cuadrado-Ballesteros, 2014; Saez-Martin, Caba-Perez and Lopez-Hernandez, 2017; Piña and Avellaneda, 2019; Keuffer and Mabillard, 2020)	United States, Spain, Chile, Switzerland Negative influence found by some of the studies on Spain.
<i>Characteristics of the local political and institutional environment</i>		
Higher political competition, with reference to the council or the mayoral race, measured as the effective number of parties in the municipality, the largest party seat share, or the difference between the electoral scores of the first and the second competitor.	(Araujo and Tejedo-Romero, 2016; Berliner, 2016; Sicáková-Beblavá, Kollárik and Sloboda, 2016; Piña and Avellaneda, 2019; Tavares and da Cruz, 2020; Michener and Nichter, 2022)	Spain, South Africa, Slovakia, Portugal, Chile, Brazil Negative influence found in Portugal.
Number of terms in office of the political leader – less time spent in office	(Sicáková-Beblavá, Kollárik and Sloboda, 2016; Piña and Avellaneda, 2019; Tavares and da Cruz, 2020)	Slovakia, Portugal, Chile
Unified government – political leader supported by a council majority from her/his own party	(Alt, Lassen and Rose, 2006; Albalate del Sol, 2013; Araujo and Tejedo-Romero, 2016; Michener and Nichter, 2022)	United States, Spain, Brazil Negative influence in Spain, limited to municipalities with right-wing mayors.
Timing of local elections – elections are near	(Cuadrado-Ballesteros, 2014)	Spain
Degree of local autonomy - higher	(Keuffer and Mabillard, 2020)	Switzerland
Local financial situation – unbalanced budget (debt or surplus)	(Alt, Lassen and Rose, 2006; Albalate del Sol, 2013; Saez-Martin, Caba-Perez and Lopez-Hernandez, 2017; Birskyte, 2019)	United States, Spain, Lithuania Positive influence in some countries and negative in others.
Local financial autonomy - lower share of intergovernmental transfers or a higher share of own revenues	(Birskyte, 2019; Tavares and da Cruz, 2020)	Portugal, Lithuania
Modes of service delivery – functional decentralization	(Cuadrado-Ballesteros, 2014)	Spain
Status of municipality – municipalities with higher political power concentration due to the presence of central government institutions (e.g., provincial capital)	(Albalate del Sol, 2013)	Spain

Explanatory factor	References	Countries and observations
<i>Characteristics of the local society and economy</i>		
Size of local government – larger local governments	(Albalate del Sol, 2013; Araujo and Tejedo-Romero, 2016; Berliner, 2016; Sicáková-Beblavá, Kollárik and Sloboda, 2016; Saez-Martin, Caba-Perez and Lopez-Hernandez, 2017; Piña and Avellaneda, 2019; Keuffer and Mabillard, 2020; Michener and Nichter, 2022)	Spain, South Africa, Slovakia, Chile, Switzerland, Brazil Negative influence in Switzerland and Lithuania.
Strength of civil society – higher number of neighbourhood organizations	(Piña and Avellaneda, 2019)	Chile
Electoral turnout - low	(Araujo and Tejedo-Romero, 2016; Birskyte, 2019; Keuffer and Mabillard, 2020)	Spain, Lithuania, Switzerland Negative influence in Lithuania.
Educational level of the population – higher	(Saez-Martin, Caba-Perez and Lopez-Hernandez, 2017)	Spain
Age of the population – higher average age	(Piotrowski and Van Ryzin, 2007; Birskyte, 2019; Tavares and da Cruz, 2020)	United States, Portugal, Lithuania Negative influence in Portugal.
Economic capacity of the population - lower unemployment	(Cuadrado-Ballesteros, 2014; Araujo and Tejedo-Romero, 2016; Sicáková-Beblavá, Kollárik and Sloboda, 2016; Saez-Martin, Caba-Perez and Lopez-Hernandez, 2017; Tavares and da Cruz, 2020)	Spain, Slovakia, Portugal Negative influence in Portugal.
Higher socio-economic development of the municipality, measured as provision of basic infrastructure, investment in the municipality, income per capita, or the degree of economic competitiveness.	(Cuadrado-Ballesteros, 2014; Araujo and Tejedo-Romero, 2016; Berliner, 2016; Birskyte, 2019; Michener and Nichter, 2022)	Spain, South Africa, Lithuania, Brazil Negative influence of income per capita in Brazil and Lithuania.
Type of municipality – urban	(Birskyte, 2019; Piña and Avellaneda, 2019; Keuffer and Mabillard, 2020)	Lithuania, Chile, Switzerland
<i>Influences from other levels of government</i>		
Neighbouring municipalities were recently subject to a transparency audit	(Michener and Nichter, 2022)	Brazil
Technical guidance from the central government, accepted voluntarily by the municipality	(Piña and Avellaneda, 2019)	Chile
Central government sanctions	(Piña and Avellaneda, 2019)	Chile

Recent research suggests that sometimes compliance and more substantial transparency are not necessarily correlated (Pernagallo and Torrisi, 2020). This makes any cross-country comparison of local government transparency quite difficult. Recently, it has been suggested that, as transparency means and achieves different things in different democratic regimes, attention should turn away from the one-size-fits-all approach toward the legal, institutional, historical, political, and cultural contexts in which transparency is defined and transparency policies are created and implemented (Grimmelikhuijsen and Kasymova, 2015; Pozen, 2020).

Efforts to explain local government compliance/transparency are also reflective of the importance of national specificities. A review of literature has observed that transparency works under certain conditions, but not others, and that more research needs to be done on contextual factors and their influence (Cucciniello, Porumbescu and Grimmelikhuijsen, 2017). In a broad perspective, researchers have focused on four categories of factors: the characteristics of local political leaders, the characteristics of the local political and institutional environment, the characteristics of local society and economy, and influences from other levels of government (see Table 1). Some of these factors, such as ideology, political competition, the size of the local government, the economic capacity of the population, and the socio-economic development of the municipality, appear more frequently. Factors found to stimulate transparency in some national contexts (ideology, political competition, unified government, local financial situation, size of local government, electoral turnout, age of population, economic capacity of the population, socio-economic development of the municipality) act as inhibitors of transparency in some others. To some extent this is visibly linked to national specificities. Political competition, for example, takes different forms in different countries. The characteristics of political leaders are likely more relevant in countries with a strong leader model of local government. More recently, the literature has moved away from looking into the effect of the exogenous characteristics of local society and economy to the endogenous characteristics of local leaders and institutions. An even more recent development focuses on estimating the impact of exogenous factors such as the sanctions or guidance provided by the central government. These shifts seem associated with the expansion of transparency research to newer democracies.

Local government transparency in the Romanian context

Local government transparency in Romania is shaped by a quite detailed legal framework, dating back to the early 2000s. Its main pillars are the Law concerning citizen access to public interest information (the FOI law, no. 544/2001) and the Law concerning decision-making transparency in local public administration (no. 52/2003), with secondary provisions inserted into other legal texts. The implementation of these laws has, however, produced less than expected transparency, as shown by both third sector organizations and researchers (APADOR-CH, 2007; Centrul de Resurse pentru Participare Publică, 2008; Cobârzan, Dragoș and Neamțu, 2008; Suciș et al., 2009; Dragoș, Neamțu and Cobârzan, 2012; Schnell, 2015, 2016; Stănuș, 2016a). The manner in which transparency provisions were introduced, by policy entrepreneurs invoking norms present in international policy discourse to advance their preferred policies and counteract resistance from various domestic actors, has likely influenced implementation (Schnell, 2015).

A few characteristics of Romanian local government are likely to shape the low degree of compliance with transparency regulations. First, due to how the decentralization process has unfolded after 1989, Romanian local governments have high burdens in terms of tasks and relatively few resources to deal with them (Profiroiu, Profiroiu and Szabo, 2017). Administrative capacity is thus an issue in transparency policy implementation (Dragoș, Neamțu and Cobârzan, 2012). However,

monitoring done by NGOs has pointed out that non-compliant high-capacity local governments as well as compliant low-capacity ones do exist. While capacity was frequently invoked, anecdotic pieces of evidence suggest an explanation of the low compliance could also be sought elsewhere.

Second, the strong leader model of first tier local government specific to Romania, which places a directly elected mayor atop of the local executive, could also shape transparency. At least one high-profile case of urban local government which, by decision of the mayor during his term in office, has refused to implement some of the transparency provisions can be identified. In fact, previous research has pondered on whether the transparency regulations leave too much discretion to local political leaders who did not internalize transparency as a norm, thus resulting in lower compliance (Cobârzan, Dragoș and Neamțu, 2008). A question which can thus be asked concerns if and which leader characteristics make it more likely that the local government complies with transparency regulations.

Third, local government transparency is shaped by the choice of implementation mechanisms. Although expecting a low degree of compliance by local governments and other governmental entities, the national decision-makers have decided to introduce rather weak enforcement mechanisms. There are no sanctions for non-compliant governmental entities, while the adjudication of all disputes is left to the quite slow judicial process. A central government entity is tasked with monitoring implementation and providing guidance. Its status varies over time (ministry, agency, or a simple department) and the periods of status downgrades seem associated with a central government emphasis on monitoring over guidance. The expectation was that the pressure exercised by civil society in one form or another and the informal supervision provided by the central government entity will push local governments toward higher degrees of compliance with transparency provisions. For a brief time, this state of things was altered during the term in office of the technocratic Cioloș government (November 2015 – January 2017). A ministry of social dialogue was charged with supervising the implementation of transparency provisions. This was not the first time these tasks were given to an entity with ministry status. What was different was the fact that the ministry was led by a team of former activists with a background in transparency monitoring third sector organizations. During this time, the ministry has applied higher than usual pressure (has provided more intensive guidance) to increase local government compliance with transparency regulations. Moreover, the technocratic government is the result of a major crisis which, at least for a while, has increased social pressure over all governmental structures. It could be reasonable to expect that local governments have also felt this pressure and reacted accordingly. A question arises from here as well. To what extent this external pressure, coming from upper levels of government or local civil society, works to increase compliance?

Fourth, citizens' demand for transparency in Romania is limited (APADOR-CH, 2007; Dragoș, Neamțu and Cobârzan, 2012; Radu, 2019). Moreover, much of the pressure exercised by organized civil society over local governments has dissipated once the funding provided to these (usually national rather than local) organizations by external donors has disappeared. Therefore, we can reasonably expect that exogenous factors in the category of characteristics of local society and economy have limited explanatory value regarding transparency compliance.

Fifth, we can expect longstanding historical, cultural, and institutional legacies that have re-emerged after the fall of communism to also influence local government compliance with transparency regulations. Historical development differences between Romania's historical provinces persist, despite the levelling up effects of the second world war and the communist regime (Benedek and Kurko, 2010). These historical development differences are also associated with different experiences

of local self-government prior to 1918 (Guțan, 2003) and, apparently, after 1989. A recent analysis of the quality of government at the regional level in Europe (Charron, Dijkstra and Lapuente, 2014, 2015) finds visible differences between Romanian regions. Micro-level analyses also suggest regional patterns persist (see for example differences in terms of attitudes of local elected officials toward governance mechanisms, Stănuș, 2016b).

Empirical strategy

In relation to the Romanian case, this paper does two things. First, it provides a measure of local government compliance with transparency regulations. Second, it builds an explanatory model of compliance, considering similar efforts made in other countries and the national specificities. In building this model three questions are being considered: Which previously identified predictors of compliance are also relevant in the Romanian context? Does external pressure exercised by the central government and/or civil society increase compliance with transparency provisions? How strong is the influence of the characteristics of the political leader in explaining compliance?

Sample and data sources. To empirically examine local government transparency compliance in Romania a dataset was built using the following sources of information: monitoring data from the Ministry of Social Dialogue; turnout and political competition data from the Permanent Electoral Authority; demographic, economic, and financial data from the National Institute of Statistics and the Ministry of Finance. The dataset (N=150) concerns all local governments entering in one of the following categories: the capital city of Bucharest and its sub-divisions of the capital city of Bucharest (sectoare, as these are equivalent to first tier local governments); county capitals (municipii reședință de județ); other urban municipalities of economic, social, or cultural importance (municipii); and counties (județe, the second tier of local government). The analysis is limited to these local governments as we can reasonably expect them to have the highest, even though not always comparable, administrative capacity. Such a strategy allows for better assessing the impact of other factors, while surpassing the difficult question of how to measure administrative capacity (El-Taliawi and Van Der Wal, 2019). Monitoring data from the Ministry of Social Dialogue concerns two different moments of time in 2016 (March and November). There are two main reasons for using this dataset rather than more recent ones. First, 2016 has seen increased top-down pressure on local governments to increase compliance. Second, local elections were organized in 2016, with a significant number of local governments seeing a change of executive leadership (mayor or president of the county council). Thus, this data allows for a better assessment of the impact of top-down pressure and political factors. All other variables in the dataset involve measurement at the closest moment of time to 2016 for which information is available.

Measurement of local government compliance. For the purposes of this paper, local government compliance with transparency regulations is measured in relation to legal provisions covering political, administrative, and financial transparency, stemming from the legal framework. A simple additive index is built using twenty items. These items reflect whether at a certain moment in time the local government had published on its website a certain piece of information which should be made available to citizens ex officio. A measurement of transparency in a broader sense would have required a weighting of the different components and, possibly, the addition of more elements (see, for example, the approach in da Cruz et al., 2016). The option for a simple additive measurement reflects that fact that legal documents against which the degree of compliance must be established does not give less or more importance to certain components. These items were identified as relevant and collected by the Ministry of Social Dialogue. The index used here departs from the one built by the

ministry for its own purposes in one key respect. For reasons not clear, the ministry has included in its measure of compliance information concerning the publication of the budget, the report on its freedom of information duties (FOI report), and the citizen participation in decision-making report for two calendar years, while for other items which need to be published each year (such as the other activity reports) only one calendar year was included. Thus, the official index gives higher weight to some items. In this paper an index which fixes this is used. The analysis employs as dependent variable both the compliance index measured in November 2016 and the change in compliance between March 2016 and November 2016.

Table 2. Measurement of local government compliance with transparency regulations.

Component of transparency	Information to be published <i>ex officio</i>
Political transparency	Leadership of institution (structure, officials) Means available for citizens to contact / meet with the leadership Strategic documents (programmes, strategies) Last annual activity reports (institutional, individual)
Financial transparency	Sources of revenue Last annual budget Last annual budget discharge Information on public procurement procedures Last annual public procurement plan Information on the salaries of staff (non-nominal)
Administrative transparency	Legal documents concerning the functioning of the local government Division of tasks between departments Operating hours Institutional contact information Name and contact data – civil servant in charge of FOI List of documents produced and/or managed List of documents of public interest Procedures for contesting local government decisions Last annual FOI report (Law 544/2001) Last annual citizen participation in decision-making report (Law 53/2002)

Potential explanatory factors of local government compliance. As shown in Table 3, three categories of factors were considered potentially relevant and included: characteristics of the local political leaders (mayors and presidents of the county councils), characteristics of the local political and institutional environment, and characteristics of the local society and economy. Both endogenous and exogenous factors are accounted for.

In the category of individual characteristics of the leaders, ideology and age are analyzed. This segment of the analysis assumes that transparency compliance is to some extent an inherently political decision. In a strong tier model of local government this decision likely rests with the political leader. Local governments led by left-leaning or progressive leaders were found to be more transparent in other national contexts. However, in the post-Communist context of Romania, the main party on the political left has been widely considered to be the successor of the Communist party and center-right parties have generally labelled themselves as being the progressive ones. Thus, we can reasonably expect that in this context ideology might operate differently. The age of the political leader is relevant in this context because older political leaders tend to also have a different personal and political experience (some of it during the Communist regime) and are more likely to respond positively to top-

down rules and pressure for compliance. Some factors in the leadership variables category are deemed relevant but not included in the analysis, as there was not enough variation in the population studied. It was the case of the gender of the political leader of the local government (mayor or president of the county council, a very small number of female leaders exist in Romania), the education of the political leader, as well as whether he or she is an independent.

Table 3. Potential explanatory factors of local government compliance with transparency regulations in Romania: measurements and expected relationships.

Explanatory factor	Direction of relationship in the literature	Expected direction of relationship	Measurement and observations
<i>Characteristics of the local political leaders</i>			
Ideology – left-leaning political leader	+	-	Dummy variable, last known political affiliation of the leader - left party
Age of the political leader	NA	+	Age in 2016
<i>Characteristics of the local political and institutional environment</i>			
High political competition	+	+	Distance between the electoral scores of the first and second competitors, local or county council, 2016 election
Shorter time spent in office by the political leader	+	+	Dummy variable, political leader at his/her first term in office
Unified local government	+	+/-	Dummy variable, political leader is supported by a council majority from his/her party (informal alliances not included)
Local financial autonomy	+	+	Share of own revenues in total revenues in 2016
Status of local government	+	+	Dummy variable, local government had the same status in 1990
<i>Characteristics of the local society and economy</i>			
Size of local government	+	+	Number of residents in January 2016
Electoral turnout	-	-	Turnout in the 2016 local elections
Historically less developed province	NA	-	Dummy variables for Eastern (Moldova + Bucovina) and Southern (Muntenia, Oltenia, Dobrogea) Romania

In the category of local political and institutional characteristics, local political competition, the existence of a unified government, the time spent in office by the political leader of the local government, local financial autonomy, and whether the local government had a change of status since 1990 are considered. Higher political competition likely reflects into more conflictual local government, case in which higher transparency, which leaves less topics for discussion by the political opposition, is likely. In line with the literature, it can be reasonably expected that there is less transparency where the same leader has held the executive office for a longer period. However, we can wonder what to expect in relation to unified local governments. Given Romania's almost tradition of 'local barons' dominating local governments (Ștefan et al., 2004), we could find less transparency where the political

leader of the local government is supported by a strong majority of her/his own party in the council, as there is no strong opposition demanding transparency. On the other hand, such dominance might also mean decision-makers feel they have nothing to hide, hence greater transparency. In the context of Romanian local government, a higher financial autonomy of the local government is a likely indicator of higher administrative capacity (more own resources means more human resources with better training) and is expected to lead to higher compliance. However, financial autonomy is an imperfect proxy for administrative capacity. Another such proxy is the status of the local government in Romania's settlement system. Since 1990, a low key territorial reform has led to a series of municipal splits and to upgrading the administrative status of some municipalities (for example from town to municipiu, urban municipality of political, administrative, economic or cultural importance), often disregarding administrative capacity criteria set by the national legislation (Stănuș, 2021). Hence, it can be expected that local governments which have experienced a change of status and have likely a lower administrative capacity to be less compliant.

Three characteristics of the local economy and society are also included: the size of the local government, turnout in the last local election, and the historical region. The size of the local government is expected to function similarly to other countries. Larger local governments with higher resources should be better positioned to comply with the demands of the transparency regime. In what concerns turnout, we can expect that the higher the turnout (as an indicator of the citizens' trust in local government) the lower the incentives to comply with the top-down transparency regime, in a manner similar to other countries. The third variable – the historical region – accounts for socio-cultural differences between Romania's different regions, differences which also reflect into their socio-economic development (Benedek and Kurko, 2010; Ianoș et al., 2013) or the strength of the local civil society (Bădescu and Sum, 2005).

Findings

The analysis shows that none of the local governments analyzed here reaches maximum compliance (see Table 4). The best performers fail to comply with one of the newer administrative transparency duties, that of periodically publishing a non-nominal document concerning the salaries paid to their staff.

Table 4. Local government compliance with transparency regulations in Romania, 2016.

Transparency compliance	Index March 2016	Index November 2016
<i>Theoretical maximum value</i>	20	20
Maximum value	19	19
Minimum value	0	0
Average	15.16	15.88
Std. dev.	3.89	3.72
Number of municipalities reaching the highest value	2	12
Number of local governments with lower compliance at the second measurement	-	14
Number of local governments with constant compliance at the second measurement	-	65
Number of local governments with higher compliance at the second measurement	-	71

When comparing data from March 2016 to data from November 2016 an overall improvement is visible, suggesting external pressure (either created by the ministry or by civil society) has stimulated compliance. There are also local governments reacting to pressure by decreasing their compliance. However, the descriptive analysis reveals no easily discernible patterns in terms of which municipalities are the best and the worst performers.

Predictors of compliance. To identify factors explaining compliance with transparency provisions two separate analyses were conducted. The first consists of a regression analysis with robust standard errors using the November 2016 index of compliance as dependent variable. The second analysis consists of a regression analysis with robust standard errors using the change of the compliance index between the two moments in time. The results are reflected in Table 5.

According to these results, local government compliance is mostly being determined by characteristics of the local political and institutional environment and by some characteristics of local society. Four variables are statistically significant: the presence of a unified local government, the status of local government, its size, and whether it is in Southern Romania. Compliance is higher if the municipality is larger, a unified local government exists, and there was no change to the status of the local government since 1990. Compliance is lower if the local government is in one of the historical provinces of Oltenia, Muntenia, or Dobrogea. Very close to the statistical significance threshold we find ideology. The sign of the coefficient suggests that contrary to the stated expectations transparency is likely higher where the political leader belongs to the political left.

Size and the fact that the local government has not experienced a change of status after 1989 work here, to some extent, as proxies for the availability of resources to deal with all the tasks. Thus, findings fit the expectation that where resources are available local governments find it easier to comply. If we link this with anecdotic evidence from previous monitoring efforts of third sector organization we can speculate over the actual mechanism at work. Larger local governments have larger numbers of civil servants; hence it is more likely they have staff dealing exclusively with transparency.

Moreover, these civil servants are more likely to be able to act autonomously in the fulfilment of their transparency-related tasks. The size of local government as a relevant predictor of compliance also (speculatively) tells another story. In what is likely a form of less explicit coercive isomorphism (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983), larger local governments experience and adapt to diffuse (implicit, informal) pressure to increase transparency, independent of explicit demands from the local civil society. This diffuse pressure stems, on the one hand, from the sheer number of citizens to be served and, on the other hand, by the expectation that larger local governments should be able to better serve citizens. The latter is likely felt stronger at the second tier of the local government, as Romanian county councils are informally expected to serve as an example for small and less resourceful first tier local governments.

The statistical linkage between a unified local government and higher compliance suggests a democratic modus operandi exists even where the same political party has secured both the executive positions and a majority in the council, which, at least in what concerns compliance with transparency regulations, contradicts the 'local barons' thesis. The likelihood that compliance is higher where the political leader of the local government belongs to the political left (similar to what has been found in other national contexts) suggests it might be the case that a 'reversal of progressiveness' is happening in Romanian politics, with Romanian parties aligning more closely to their counterparts in western contexts on various policy issues.

Table 5. Predictors of local government compliance with transparency regulations in Romania.

Independent variables Dependent variables	Model 1 - Compliance with transparency regulations in November 2016			Model 2 - Change in compliance March – November 2016		
	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	P>t	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	P>t
Ideology <i>Left-leaning political leader</i>	1.126	0.640	0.081	0.083	0.263	0.750
Age	0.011	0.035	0.755	0.028	0.012	0.030
Political competition	-0.049	0.034	0.153	-0.004	0.007	0.584
Time in office <i>Leader at first term</i>	0.083	0.653	0.899	-0.063	0.257	0.806
Unified local government <i>Leader supported by majority from own party</i>	1.639	0.823	0.048	-0.265	0.252	0.296
Local financial autonomy	0.033	0.032	0.310	0.021	0.009	0.029
Status of local government <i>No change since 1990</i>	3.271	1.039	0.002	-0.691	.314	0.030
Size of local government	2.09	9.65	0.032	-1.25	3.50	0.000
Turnout	0.078	0.064	0.229	-0.000	0.020	0.987
Less developed province <i>Eastern Romania</i>	-0.637	0.725	0.381	0.161	0.299	0.590
<i>Southern Romania</i>	-2.185	0.735	0.004	0.188	0.278	0.500
_cons	7.577	5.498	0.170	-0.799	1.525	0.601
Model fit	N = 150, F(11, 138) = 2.98, Prob > F = 0.0014, R-squared = 0.23 , Mean VIF = 1.56			N = 150, F(11, 138) = 4.99, Prob > F = 0.0000, R-squared = 0.24 , Mean VIF = 1.56		

Lower compliance with transparency regulations in Southern Romania (the historical provinces of Oltenia, Muntenia, and Dobrogea) confirms our expectations of a regional pattern. It is however difficult to discern what is behind this regional pattern: institutional legacies, socio-economic development reflecting into resources available to the local government, or the strength of local civil society and its ability to pressure local governments.

The change (increase) in compliance between March and November 2016, in response to the pressure exercised by the Ministry of Social Dialogue, is partially explained by some of the same factors. Four variables are significant in this model: the age of the political leader, local financial autonomy, the status of the local government, and its size. There is a slight positive change if the political leader is older. It is likely that higher experience in intergovernmental relations translates into higher responsiveness to requests coming from the central government. There is a slight positive change if the local government has a higher degree of financial autonomy. There is significant negative change if the local government has not changed its status (bivariate analysis shows all local governments performing worse in November 2016 have not changed status, while all local governments experiencing a change of status since 1990 have increased their performance). There is also significant negative change in the case of larger local governments. Pieced together, these results suggest mixed responses from local governments to the pressure exercised by the central government. Local political and institutional characteristics are again key to explaining change in the dependent variable.

While the larger size and status stability of the local governments explain higher voluntary compliance, they also explain a decrease in compliance following top-down pressures coming from the central government. However, the effectively autonomous local governments (those with higher financial autonomy) respond positively to top-down pressures and increase their compliance. This suggests there are likely two competing views on intergovernmental relations at play here. The 'pragmatics' (local governments led by more experienced political leaders, local governments with higher financial autonomy) cooperate with the central government on a topic they likely perceive as minor to maintain good relations. The 'idealists' value their subjective autonomy given by size and status and are less cooperative with the central government in its efforts to increase compliance.

Conclusion

Against previous findings in the literature concerning the explanatory factors of local government compliance with transparency regulations, this paper shows that Romania has its own distinct profile. Few of the factors identified in other national contexts are relevant to explain compliance. Two out of four significant factors are from the category of characteristics of the local political and institutional environment (unified government, status of local government). The other two (size, local government in Southern Romania) are characteristics of local society. It must be noted that the first three factors are also found to be relevant in across several national contexts. Against expectations, formulated in this paper and elsewhere in the literature there is little influence of the characteristics of the political leader of the local government in explaining compliance. The political ideology of the leaders seems to have an influence, although the statistical significance threshold is not reached.

The data available also allowed for an assessment of how local governments react to pressure, exercised especially by the central government, to increase their compliance with transparency regulations. The analysis shows mixed responses, as some local governments have responded to the pressure, they likely considered unfitting of their local autonomy, by decreasing their compliance. The search for the explanatory factors of the change in compliance again points to the characteristics of the local political and institutional environment. The financial autonomy, status, and size of local

government help explain the change in compliance. However, while the status and size account for higher compliance before the central government has started to pressure local governments, they also account for decreased compliance afterwards. A single characteristic of the political leader – the age, helps explain the change in compliance.

These results on Romania support the recent turn in the literature toward looking in more detail at the endogenous characteristics of local leaders and institutions, as opposed to the previous focus on exogenous characteristics. They suggest some similarities with countries such as Spain, South Africa, Chile, Brazil, or Slovakia. It must be noted here that, except for studies on the United States, the bulk of the predictors of transparency literature focuses on second and/or third wave democracies. The fact that endogenous characteristics (unified government, status of municipality) are found to be relevant likely suggests a diversity of the organizational field of local government in what regards transparency compliance (isomorphism in progress). This is reflective of the sometimes mature, sometimes immature democratic context provided by Romania.

The results in what concerns the relevant exogenous characteristics (especially the role of regional differences) support the observation previously made in the literature (Michener, 2019; Pozen, 2020) about the importance of contextualizing research on the predictors of transparency. The relevance of local government size, which is the predictor most frequently found to explain higher transparency across different other national contexts (see Table 1), suggest we should not forego the idea of building a minimal/base model explaining transparency applicable across various national contexts. However, building such a model would likely require that first wave democracies are also studied.

There are, of course, limitations which invite caution in reading the results. The data on transparency compliance was collected by a central government entity with a specific agenda, which has likely influenced the process of data collection. To the extent possible, obvious bias in the data was corrected. A key feature of this data, that it only provides measurements of transparency for the most important urban municipalities and for the counties, is at the same time a limitation and an advantage. Data applicable to a wider range of local governments (a larger N) would have undoubtedly provided a better picture. However, this limited dataset provides the opportunity for a much better control of the influence of local government capacity, which is still quite difficult to measure in a meaningful way. The limited number of cases has of course influenced the number of factors whose influence was assessed in the multi-variate analysis. Some potentially relevant explanatory variables (such as the gender, education, or the independent status of the political leaders) were excluded due to limited variation in this sample.

Some points for practitioners of transparency in Romania and elsewhere can, nevertheless, be made. The paper shows that in a weak transparency regime where no sanctions exist for non-compliant local governments exercising top-down pressure for higher compliance is a limitative approach. Some local governments have responded positively to these pressures while others have gone the other way and effectively decreased compliance. The reasons for this more likely reside in the nature of intergovernmental relations in Romania. The relevance of size, status, financial autonomy, or social and economic development, alongside the lack of relevance of political variables, suggests higher transparency in Romania is a matter of capacity. More effective central government policy in this respect would likely be to reshape its efforts (which were significantly diminished in time, Stănuș, 2022) to provide guidance and technical assistance to the local governments.

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References

- Albalade del Sol, D. (2013). The institutional, economic and social determinants of local government transparency. *Journal of Economic Policy Reform*, 16(1), 90–107.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17487870.2012.759422>.
- Alt, J.E., Lassen, D.D. and Rose, S. (2006). The Causes of Fiscal Transparency: Evidence from the U.S. States, *IMF Staff Papers*, 53(1), 30–57. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30036021>.
- APADOR-CH (2007). *Transparența decizională în administrația publică în România anulul 2007: context, constatări și perspective*. București: APADOR-CH. Available at:
<http://www.apador.org/publicatii/trans2007.pdf>.
- Araujo, J.F.F.E. de and Tejedó-Romero, F. (2016). Local government transparency index: determinants of municipalities' rankings. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 29(4), 327–347. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPSM-11-2015-0199>.
- Bădescu, G. and Sum, P. (2005). Historical Legacies, Social Capital and Civil Society: Comparing Romania on a Regional Level. *Europe-Asia Studies*, 57(1), 117–133.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0966813052000314138>.
- Bauhr, M. and Grimes, M. (2012). What is government transparency? *QoG Working Paper Series*, 2012(16). Available at: https://www.gu.se/sites/default/files/2020-05/2012_16_Bauhr_Grimes.pdf.
- Benedek, J. and Kurko, I. (2010). Evoluția și caracteristicile disparităților teritoriale din România, pp. 77-120. În M. Bakk and J. Benedek (Eds.) *Politicele regionale în România*. Iași: Polirom.
- Berliner, D. (2016). Sunlight or Window Dressing? Local Government Compliance with South Africa's Promotion of Access to Information Act. *Governance*, 30(4), 641–661.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/gove.12246>.
- Birskyte, L. (2019). Determinants of Budget Transparency in Lithuanian Municipalities. *Public Performance & Management Review*, 42(3), 707–731.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15309576.2018.1507915>.
- Centrul de Resurse pentru Participare Publică (2008). *Există participare publică în România?* Bucharest: Centrul de Resurse pentru Participare Publică. Available at:
http://www.publicinfo.ro/library/sc/studiu_cultura_civica.pdf.
- Charron, N., Dijkstra, L. and Lapuente, V. (2014). Regional Governance Matters: Quality of Government within European Union Member States. *Regional Studies*, 48(1), 68–90.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2013.770141>.
- Charron, N., Dijkstra, L. and Lapuente, V. (2015). Mapping the Regional Divide in Europe: A Measure for Assessing Quality of Government in 206 European Regions. *Social Indicators Research*, 122(2), 315–346. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-014-0702-y>.
- Cobârzan, B.V., Dragoș, D. and Neamțu, B. (2008). Free Access to Public Information: Enforcement, Appeals and Judicial Review. A Comparative Perspective from CEE Countries. *Transylvanian Review of Administrative Sciences*, 4(24), 53–63.

- da Cruz, N.F., Tavares, A.F., Marques, R.C., Jorge, S. and de Sousa, L. (2016). Measuring Local Government Transparency. *Public Management Review*, 18(6), 866–893. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2015.1051572>.
- Cuadrado-Ballesteros, B. (2014). The impact of functional decentralization and externalization on local government transparency. *Government Information Quarterly*, 31(2), 265–277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2013.10.012>.
- Cucciniello, M. and Nasi, G. (2014). Transparency for Trust in Government: How Effective is Formal Transparency? *International Journal of Public Administration*, 37(13), 911–921. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01900692.2014.949754>.
- Cucciniello, M., Porumbescu, G.A. and Grimmeliikhuijsen, S. (2017). 25 Years of Transparency Research: Evidence and Future Directions. *Public Administration Review*, 77(1), 32–44. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.12685>.
- DiMaggio, P.J. and Powell, W.W. (1983). The Iron Cage Revisited: Institutional Isomorphism and Collective Rationality in Organizational Fields. *American Sociological Review*, 48(2), 147–160. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2095101>.
- Dragoș, D.C., Neamțu, B. and Cobârzan, B.V. (2012). Procedural transparency in rural Romania: linking implementation with administrative capacity? *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 78(1), 134–157. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852311430283>.
- El-Taliawi, O.G. and Van Der Wal, Z. (2019). Developing administrative capacity: an agenda for research and practice. *Policy Design and Practice*, 2(3), 243–257. <https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2019.1595916>.
- Etzioni, A. (2010). Is transparency the best disinfectant? *Journal of Political Philosophy*, 18(4), 389–404. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9760.2010.00366.x>.
- Grigorescu, A. (2002). European institutions and unsuccessful norm transmission: The case of transparency. *International Politics*, 39(4), 467–489. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.ip.8892005>.
- Grimmeliikhuijsen, S. and Kasymova, J. (2015). Not So Universal After All: Exploring the Meaning and Use of Government Transparency in Consensual and Majoritarian Democracies. *Public Integrity*, 17(4), 389–407. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10999922.2015.1077040>.
- Guțan, M. (2003). *Istoria administrației publice românești*. Sibiu: Editura Universității Lucian Blaga din Sibiu.
- Ianoș, I., Petrișor, A.-I., Zamfir, D., Cercleux, A.-L., Stoica, I.-V. and Tălângă, C. (2013). In search of a relevant index measuring territorial disparities in a transition country. Romania as a case study. *Die Erde*, 144(1), 69–81. <https://doi.org/10.12854/erde-144-5>.
- Keuffer, N. and Mabillard, V. (2020). Administrative openness and diversity in Swiss municipalities: how does local autonomy influence transparency practices? *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 86(4), 782–798. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852318823278>.
- Michener, G. (2019). Gauging the Impact of Transparency Policies. *Public Administration Review*, 79(1), 136–139. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.13011>.
- Michener, G. and Nichter, S. (2022). Local compliance with national transparency legislation. *Government Information Quarterly*, 39(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2021.101659>.
- Pernagallo, G. and Torrisi, B. (2020). A logit model to assess the transparency of Italian public administration websites. *Government Information Quarterly*, 37(4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2020.101519>.

- Piña, G. and Avellaneda, C. (2019). Central Government Strategies to Promote Local Governments' Transparency: Guidance or Enforcement? *Public Performance & Management Review*, 42(2), 357–382. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15309576.2018.1462215>.
- Piotrowski, S.J. (2010). The operationalization of municipal transparency: Primary administrative functions and intervening factors. *Transparencia Y Privacidad*, 1(1), 1–31.
- Piotrowski, S.J. and Van Ryzin, G.G. (2007). Citizen Attitudes Toward Transparency in Local Government. *The American Review of Public Administration*, 37(3), 306–323. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0275074006296777>.
- Pozen, D.E. (2020). Seeing Transparency More Clearly. *Public Administration Review*, 80(2), 326–331. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.13137>.
- Profiroiu, C.M., Profiroiu, A.G. and Szabo, S.R. (2017). The Decentralization Process in Romania. In J.M. Ruano and M. Profiroiu (Eds.) *The Palgrave Handbook of Decentralisation in Europe* (pp. 353–387). Cham: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-32437-1_14.
- Radu, B. (2019). The impact of transparency on the citizen participation in decision-making at the municipal level in Romania. *Central European Public Administration Review*, 17, 111–130. <https://doi.org/10.17573/cepar.2019.1.06>.
- Saez-Martin, A., Caba-Perez, C. and Lopez-Hernandez, A. (2017). Freedom of information in local government: rhetoric or reality? *Local Government Studies*, 43(2), 245–273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03003930.2016.1269757>.
- Schnell, S. (2015). Mimicry, Persuasion, or Learning? The Case of Two Transparency and Anti-Corruption Policies in Romania. *Public Administration and Development*, 35(4), 277–287. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pad.1721>.
- Schnell, S. (2016). From information to predictability: transparency on the path to democratic governance. The case of Romania. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 84(4), 692–710. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852316648756>.
- Sicáková-Beblavá, E., Kollárik, M. and Sloboda, M. (2016). Exploring the determinants of transparency of Slovak municipalities. *NISPAcee Journal of Public Administration and Policy*, 9(2), 121–145. <https://doi.org/10.1515/nispa-2016-0017>.
- Spáč, P., Voda, P. and Zagrapan, J. (2018). Does the freedom of information law increase transparency at the local level? Evidence from a field experiment. *Government Information Quarterly*, 35(3), 408–417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2018.05.003>.
- Stănuș, C. (2016a). Între detalii formale și semnificație democratică: o analiză calitativă a rapoartelor de activitate ale aleșilor locali. Raport de cercetare elaborat în cadrul proiectului Cetățenie activă pentru o bună guvernare locală transparentă. Cluj-Napoca: Centrul pentru Politici Publice.
- Stănuș, C. (2016b). Political Representation and Governance: The Case of Second-Tier Councilors in Romania. *Transylvanian Review of Administrative Sciences*, 12(48), 124–144.
- Stănuș, C. (2021). Territorial fragmentation in post-communist Romania: the not so curious case of a de-amalgamation reform. *Miscellanea Geographica*, 25(1), 62–70. <https://doi.org/10.2478/mgrsd-2020-0044>.
- Stănuș, C. (2022). Under Construction: Local Government Transparency in a New Democracy. *Filosofija. Sociologija*, 33(2). <https://doi.org/10.6001/fil-soc.v33i2.4713>.
- Ștefan, L., Grecu, R., Todor, A. and Cristescu, R. (2004). Local elections 2004: a turning point in Romanian politics. *Romanian Journal of Society and Politics*, 4(2), 66–126.

Suciu, A.M., Pop, D., Kiss, T. and Barna, G. (2009). *Consolidarea transparenței în instituții ale administrației publice județene*. Cluj-Napoca: CENPO.

Tavares, A.F. and da Cruz, N.F. (2020). Explaining the transparency of local government websites through a political market framework. *Government Information Quarterly*, 37(3).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2017.08.005>.